

Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess Biography by Brian Paul Kaess

Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess (or Käß) was born January 9, 1947, in Heutingsheim (now Freiberg am Neckar), Württemberg, Germany. This was in Lower Swabia. He was the second child of Paul Ernst Kaess and Dorothea “Doris” Dorschke. He came from a long line of Kaess’ from the Neckar Valley and his mother hailed from Upper Silesia (now Poland). His older sister, Elke Angelika Kaess, died just days after birth. He also had two younger half-sisters: Arnhild Kaess and Ursula ‘Uschi’ Karoline Berta Kaess.

He was baptized Catholic by a Lutheran pastor in a Lutheran church—something unusual, but not unheard of. This was at the request of his mother, Doris, who wanted Gerd to be Catholic. Her death in 1951 certainly left a *vacuum* in Gerd’s life. After Doris’s passing, he was later confirmed Lutheran in 1961 at the behest of his stepmother, Hildegard Golz. He grew up in *idyllic* 1950s West Germany and was adored by his half-sister, Arnhild Kaess. In this respect, his early beginnings must have felt like something out of a *Heimat* episode.

He attended the Mörike Gymnasium in Ludwigsburg and also received vocational training afterward, perhaps as a printer. He did not have to serve his conscription time in the West German military due to a physical condition, according to Arnhild Kaess. She emphasized that his problem was not psychological.

In 1965, he experienced a “wanderlust” and emigrated from West Germany to the Chicago area. There was also tensions between himself and Hildegard, which may have led him to seek more independence and depart for America. A “pull” factor for immigration may have been his Kulhanek cousins, who had preceded him to America in 1956. This may have been an example of ‘chain’ migration.

Gerd, or ‘Gert’ as he was known in America, studied at Loyola University Chicago, according to family lore, though no transcript has ever been found. Nonetheless, the Kaess family lived at 1020 W. Loyola Avenue at the time of the twins’ birth, suggesting a Loyola connection. His cousin, Roland Kulhanek, and wife Marie insisted that Gerd went to college. It was rumored he wanted to study journalism at Loyola.

It was also rumored that he met his future wife, Marie Ellen Dawson, at a Loyola fraternity party. They wed on September 30, 1967, in Chicago, when she was pregnant with their twin sons: Brian Paul Kaess and Garret Thomas Kaess. So, this was a bit of a ‘shotgun’ marriage. Nonetheless, the twins were born legitimate and not ‘unehelich,’ entering the world in Chicago on October 24, 1967.

It was said Gerd worked as a printer and even held three jobs to support his family. One record also indicates ‘laborer.’ In addition, there was a yarn that he had an American girlfriend—this was the dawning of the *Age of Aquarius*, after all! Gerd & Marie were both part of the Hippie culture that spread rapidly in the 1960s. Moreover, it was said Gerd and Marie had taken Brian & Garret on a road trip in a VW minivan to either Wisconsin or Canada, and Brian remembers falling harmlessly out of the driver’s side window, onto a pile of Fall leaves, when the van was parked. As a hippie, Gerd was known to have used drugs, at least marijuana. In fact, both twins remember being at their high-rise apartment on Sheridan Avenue when Gerd and his friends were having a marijuana party—the smog of the product being ripe in the air.

Gerd died tragically on October 20, 1972, in Chicago, at the early age of 25, from an accidental drug and alcohol overdose, suffering an ill-starred fate. This occurred in the Lakeview neighborhood on the North Side. The dangers of drugs weren't fully known to the public back then and this may have been a factor in the circumstances leading up to his demise. Before he died, he had been working on a toy model gas station for his twins' fifth birthday. Sadly, it was left incomplete.

His sisters in Germany were heartbroken that he had died alone. The Kulhanek family, along with Marie and her twins, attended the wake and funeral—perhaps at Oakridge Cemetery in Maywood, Illinois. Brian even remembers walking up to the open casket and touching his father's hand. Marie & her twins bore their grief with *taciturn* silence, with none of the studied advertisements of sorrow. The loss that had befallen them was *emblematic* of a poverty that would shadow them into the future. Nonetheless, Gerd was a beautiful, gentle person, and he was sorely missed- his death leaving a 'lacuna' in the family for years to come. Despite this terrible loss, the Kaess twins would rise like the *phoenix* and go on to have cherished families of their own, becoming a case study in resilience.